

“A Study To Assess The Knowledge Regarding The Benefits Of Therapeutic Foot Massage Among Nurses Working At Selected Hospitals, Udupi With A View To Develop An Information Booklet.”

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ABSTRACT

Pain is a human response to illness; it is experienced by patients suffering from a broad spectrum of diseases. The International Association for the Study of Pain defines pain as "an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage". Convenient sampling technique was used to select 100 staff nurses working at selected hospitals of Udupi. Inventory used are Demographic Proforma and Structured knowledge Questionnaire Likert scale to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding benefits of therapeutic foot massage. Ethical clearance and administrative permission were obtained prior to the study. Overall assessment of knowledge score of nurses in that majority 66 (66%) staff nurses had poor knowledge level, 28 (28%) staff nurses had moderate knowledge, 6 (6%) staff nurses had good knowledge and none of them had excellent knowledge on therapeutic foot massage. Area-wise analysis of Knowledge of staff nurses regarding therapeutic foot massage shows that overall knowledge mean was 8.87 with standard deviation of 2.801 and mean percentage was 39.62. Further, there was no association of knowledge scores with selected demographic variables. The variables namely age, gender, educational qualification, years of experience, previous knowledge and source of information at 0.05 level of significance, do not show any significant association. The study concluded that majority of staff nurses had lack of knowledge regarding therapeutic foot massage. Hence there is a need to improve knowledge of the nurses regarding therapeutic foot massage.

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defined health in 1946 as "a state of complete physical, mental, an social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity."¹ With the advent of the 21st century maintaining this state of health is becoming more challenging. The changes in the life styles have fundamentally changed the quality of life of people during past 100 years, resulting in an increase in the global disease burden.¹

Our bodies are made up of billions of cells that grow, divide, and then die in a predictable manner. Cancer occurs when something goes wrong with this system, causing uncontrolled cell division and growth.²

Pain is a human response to illness; it is experienced by patients suffering from a broad spectrum of diseases. The International Association for the Study of Pain defines pain as "an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage". Inherent in the definition is the recognition that pain perception, management, and evaluation are influenced by multiple integral factors, including physical, psychological, social, cultural, and environmental perspectives unique to the affected person. Because pain is a subjective and uniquely individual experience, pain management can pose challenges for the patient and health care provider².

Postoperative pain assessment and management remains one of the major clinical challenges confronting health-care professionals. Abdominal surgery tends to be the most painful among all surgery types, and 70% of patients who undergo upper abdominal surgery suffer from severe pain. Nurses play a major role in minimizing pain and discomfort. It is essential for providers and nurses to assess, monitor, and provide pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic interventions for those who complain of pain or discomfort, so that the patient will return to self-care and normal daily functioning in a reasonable amount of time³.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To assess the knowledge regarding therapeutic foot massage among nurses working at selected hospitals, Udupi.
- To assess find out the association between knowledge scores with selected demographic variables.
- To develop an informational booklet regarding benefits of therapeutic foot massage.

CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Based on Beckner MH, Stretcher V and Rosenstock IM (1997)

Methodology:

Convenient sampling technique was used to select 100 staff nurses working at selected hospitals of Udupi. Inventory used are Demographic Proforma and Structured Questionnaire Likert scale to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding benefits of therapeutic foot massage. Ethical clearance and administrative permission were obtained prior to the study.

Data collection methods

Sociodemographic data namely age in years, Gender, Educational qualification, years of experience and clinical characteristics of the previous knowledge on therapeutic foot massage and source of information on therapeutic foot massage were utilized to assess the knowledge. All the tools were validated by 10 experts from the subjected and established content validity. The pilot study was conducted and the tools were found reliable using split half method by Spearman Brown Prophecy formula. The reliability obtained was ($r=0.85$). Structured knowledge questionnaires had 40 questions from various aspects of therapeutic foot massage. The data on knowledge was organized as adequate knowledge level and inadequate knowledge based on the mean value.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were recorded systematically and analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistics at a 5% level of significance using IBM SPSS version 23 software. The Knowledge and attitude of health promotion activities were analyzed using frequency and percentage. The relationship between knowledge and attitude was assessed by using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient. The association of the knowledge and attitude of health promotion activities with selected demographic variables was analyzed using the chi-square test.

Result and Analysis

TABLE 1: distribution of nurses based on their demographic characteristics

N=100

Sl. No	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Age in year		
	a) 20-24	58	58 %
	b) 25-29	26	26%
	c) 30-34	10	10%
	d) 35-39	02	02%
	e) Above 40	04	04%
2	Gender		
	a)Male	14	14%
	b)Female	86	86%
3	Educational qualification		
	a) GNM	82	82%
	b) BSc./PBBS. Nursing	18	18%
	c) MSc. Nursing	00	--
4	Years of experience		
	a) < 1 year	56	56%
	b) 1-3 years	24	24%
	c) >3 years	20	20%
5	Previous knowledge of therapeutic foot massage		
	a) Yes	28	28%
	b) No	72	72%
6	Source of information		
	a)Friends/ Family	18	18%
	b)Mass media	10	10%
	c) None	72	72%

Table : 2 Distribution of the samples on therapeutic foot massage knowledge
N=100

SL.NO	Overall knowledge of nurses	Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1	POOR KNOWLEDGE	0-7	66	66 %
2	MODERATE KNOWLEDGE	8-14	28	28 %
3	GOOD KNOWLEDGE	15-22	06	06%
4	EXCELLENT KNOWLEDGE	23-30	00	00
TOTAL		30	100	100 %

FIG 2: GRAPH SHOWING OVERALL KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF NURSES.

TABLE –3:

AREA-WISE ANALYSIS OF KNOWLEDGE OF STAFF NURSES REGARDING THERAPEUTIC FOOT MASSAGE

N=100

SL. NO	AREA	MAXIMUM POSSIBLE SCORE	MEAN	MEAN PERCENTAGE	STANDARD DEVIATION (SD)
1	INTRODUCTION	01	0.48	48.33	0.504
2	DEFINITION	02	0.75	37.50	0.728
3	FOOT MASSAGE	02	0.65	32.50	0.577
4	INDICATION	01	0.48	48.33	0.504
5	BENEFITS	08	1.97	39.33	0.938
6	MECHANISM OF FOOT MASSAGE	05	1.50	37.50	0.911
7	TECHNIQUES	06	1.50	37.50	0.873
8	STEPS OF FOOT MASSAGE	03	0.57	18.89	0.673
9	CONTRAINDICATION	01	0.48	48.33	0.504
10	CONCLUSION	01	0.49	48.02	0.522
	TOTAL	30	8.87	39.62	2.801

TABLE –3: DISTRIBUTION OF THE SAMPLES ON ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND KNOWLEDGE SCORES

SL.NO	Demographic value	Chi- square value	Df	P- value	Significance
1	Age in years	2.611	1	0.106	NS
2	Gender	0.303	1	0.582	NS
3	Educational qualification	0.549	1	0.459	NS
4	Years of experience	0.923	1	0.337	NS
5	Previous knowledge	0.451	1	0.502	NS
6	Source of information	1.065	1	0.302	NS

Significant at 0.05 level

NS: Non-significant

DISCUSSION

In the present study majority of the samples, 58% were belongs to the age group of 20-24 years, distribution of gender revealed that 86% were females, professional qualification of subjects majority of the 82% were GNM and 56% were having < 1 years of experience.

The current study showed that majority of the samples, 72% were not having any previous knowledge about foot massage and 72% were unaware about therapeutic foot massage.

There was a significant association between the knowledge scores of nurses and their selected demographic variables namely age, gender, educational qualification, years of experience, previous knowledge and source of information at 0.05 level of significance.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that majority of staff nurses had lack of knowledge regarding therapeutic foot massage. Hence there is a need to improve knowledge of the nurses regarding therapeutic foot massage.

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